

CLIMAREST

Report on co-creation workshop for the
task T 3.3 C. Structures Arctic

	Project number: 101093865 Project duration: 1 Dec 2022 – 30 Nov 2025 Project coordinator: Ida Beathe Øverjordet, SINTEF Ocean Web site: www.climarest.eu		
	Deliverable ID: not applicable	Due month: not applicable	Preparation date: 2024-02-14
	Title: Report		
	Lead beneficiary: Longyearbyen Lokalstyre, Port of Longyearbyen		
	Prepared by: Anatoly O. Sinitsyn (SINTEF AS), Ingebrigt Uglem (NINA), and Yennie K. Bredin (NINA)		

Abstract

This report presents organization of and results from a co-creation workshop for development of a prototype for erosion protection of permafrost coastlines in Longyearbyen, Svalbard, Norway. The fundamental principle behind the development process is that it should represent a compromise between needs for urban development, conservation of biodiversity, practical realism, sustainability, and efficiency for protection against erosion. The results from the co-creating workshop show that the emphasis on human needs/recreational potential was more pronounced than expected. This could partly be a result of a skewed composition among the attending stakeholders, but it is not unreasonable to assume that it also may reflect the general public opinion in Longyearbyen. It was highlighted that information and involvement during the construction phase would be beneficial.

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission services)	
CI	Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC)	

Deliverable type

R	Document, report	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

Authorship information

Editors	Anatoly O. Sinitsyn, Ingebrigt Uglem, and Yennie K. Bredin
Contributing partners	SINTEF AS, NINA

Version history

Version number	Date	Description of changes
1	January 24 2024	Second version of report (one typo on 3 rd page is fixed). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10561358

Appendix: none.

1. Introduction

This report presents results from the co-creation workshop for the task “T3.3 C. structures Arctic” in the CLIMAREST project [1]. The workshop was held in Longyearbyen (Svalbard) on September 5th 2023. This workshop was *not* a part of any developments run by the authorities in Longyearbyen. The event was organized at the ARTICA studio [2]. A general description of the event, co-creation activities and main findings are presented.

Svalbard is an archipelago located in the Arctic Ocean between the Norwegian mainland and the North Pole (Figure 1). Administered by Norway, this region hosts a variety of permanent settlements and research stations. These include Longyearbyen and Barentsburg, both permanent communities, as well as the permanent research settlement of Ny-Ålesund, the Hornsund research station, and the decommissioned coal-mining settlement of Svea. In addition, several abandoned mining settlements can be found in the archipelago, including Pyramiden, Grumant and Coles Bay. Longyearbyen is the largest settlement on Svalbard with approximately 3000 inhabitants [3].

Figure 1. Overview map of Svalbard (© OpenStreetMap Contributors (2017)). Distributed under the Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL) v1.0.

Structure of this report:

1. Introduction
2. Methodology
3. Results
4. Discussion and conclusions
5. References

There are two supplements that follow this report:

- Presentation "Towards NBS for coastal protection in cold regions – the ClimaRest perspective" that was held at a meeting of American Society® of Civil Engineers (ASCE) [4] on October 25th 2023 [5].

This presentation is similar to the presentation that was given at the workshop. Minor deviations are related to some illustrations that were modified for better clarity, and the slides with results obtained during the workshop.

- Excel table "Results of workshop Svalbard 2023" [6].

This table presents the results of the co-creation discussion held during the workshop. The results are presented in two summary tables:

- Summary on identified issues, sheet "Issues".
- Summary on suggested solutions, sheet "Solutions".

The task "T3.3 C. structures Arctic" in the CLIMAREST project involves development of a blueprint for the establishment of a nature-based structural solution for protection of permafrost-affected coastlines against coastal erosion. The blueprint will include design and construction of a full-scale prototype. Longyearbyen was selected as test area (i.e., the area where a prototype will be constructed) as its coastline is heavily exposed to coastal erosion [5, 7-9], both in the urban areas and in the more undisturbed coastal stretches that host objects of cultural heritage [10].

The CLIMAREST study sites in Longyearbyen area are comprised of [5](Figure 2):

- Coastal stretch "City quay - Old quay" - the main site. This site is in an urban settings and suffers from coastal erosion that threatens infrastructure.
- Coastal stretch at the historical settlement of Hiorthhamn, where coastal erosion is threatening Taubanestasjonen ("The turning station", an historical cable car station)[10] that was used for coal loading on the ships. This site serves as reference and replication site.
- Additional reference sites at Vestpynten and Revneset (both in proximity of Longyearbyen).

Figure 2. CLIMAREST study sites in Longyearbyen area. Maps: overview map of Svalbard: © OpenStreetMap Contributors (2017), distributed under the Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL) v1.0.; maps and aerial images of Longyearbyen: © TopoSvalbard, Norwegian Polar Institute.

The blueprint consists of the following:

- Part A: Vision for the coastal stretch "New quay - Old quay" (approximately 340 m long shoreline)
- Part B: Design, construction, and testing of a prototype for coastal protection at the coastal stretch "New quay - Old quay" (approximately 10-20 m long)
- Part C: Vision and data collection for replication/reference site at Hiorthhamn

Development of the blueprint is based on a compromise between urban development, conservation of biodiversity and practical realism. Following the restoration continuum of the Society for Ecological Restoration [11], the aim for the blueprint Part A and Part B corresponds to the stages "Remediation" (Improving ecosystem management, at least) and "Rehabilitation" (Repairing ecosystem function, at best).

2. Methodology

The goal of the workshop was twofold:

1. To present the CLIMAREST project [1] to the general public of Longyearbyen. The presentation provided general information about the project, and specific information about the blueprints (prototypes) for the coastal areas "Bykaia - Gammelkaia" ("New quay - Old quay") in Longyearbyen and in Hiorthhamn. Potential prototype solutions were outlined during the workshop, but no detailed design was presented.
2. To conduct an interactive co-creation session with public stakeholders in Longyearbyen to identify potential issues and solutions for development of the coastal stretch "New quay - Old quay". The purpose of the interactive session was twofold; 1) to gather feedback on the outlined blueprint for the "New quay - Old quay" coastal stretch, and 2) to perform a co-creation act/activity that would provide input to the outlined blueprint.

The initial design of the blueprint was based on our own understanding of the design process that needed to be a compromise between 1) needs for urban development, 2) conservation of biodiversity, 3) practical realism, 4) sustainability (i.e. sustainable production and use of materials) and 5) efficiency for protection against erosion. From the beginning of the project, we have envisioned that development of blueprints must include a co-creation part. Co-creation was chosen as an approach to collaborate with relevant stakeholders such that these could contribute to the design process. In particular, it was an aim that the co-creation process should contribute to the development of a vision, as well as development of functional and sustainable technical solutions for preventing further coastal erosion at the stretch "New quay - Old quay".

Our approach corresponds well with the "Living shorelines" approach [12] of NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, USA). Existing guidelines of NOAA focus on sheltered coasts [12, 13], yet the interest of NOAA for applying this approach "along all coasts" is pointed out in [12]. Existing [12] do however not cover permafrost coastlines. One of the NOAA's guiding principles for Living shorelines is "early coordination across multiple government and non-governmental entities to discuss site characteristics, history of erosion at the site, *and potential challenges for proposed management approaches*" (p. 9 in [12]). In our opinion, this principle, especially the part highlighted in *Italics*, corresponds to the approach of co-creation [14] as this is used in many domains of design, as well as in CLIMAREST.

In the co-creation workshop, we followed the main principles of co-creation and design thinking, which for example may be found in [14]. The following steps were executed in the light of [14]:

1. An overview of what we wanted to examine, i.e., the blueprints that were developed by CLIMAREST up to the date:
 - Part A: Vision for the coastal stretch "New quay – Old quay" (approximately 340 m long shoreline), see slide 33–36 in [5].
 - Part B: Design, construction and testing of a prototype for coastal protection at the coastal stretch "New quay – Old quay" (approximately 10–20 m long), see slide 37 in [5].
2. Determining the aim (of the blueprints), i.e., that in the end of the design phase the blueprints would represent practical and innovative solutions that are ecologically, socially, sustainably, and economically sound.
3. Deciding the target audience of the workshop – the goal was to identify all stakeholders who may have their "shares" in the problem. To our best understanding, this should include the residents ("old-timers" and "new-commers"), the local authority owning responsibility for the coastal stretch in question, the local and central authorities, local business associations, local tourist operators, representatives from industries located in the area, local sport organizations and consultancy companies working in the area.

Announcement for the co-creation workshop was published in the local newspaper SvalbardPosten (mobile version, desk-top version, and print version, see Figure 3), flyers were placed at the information desk of the local library, invitations were sent to relevant organized stakeholders via e-mail (but not to residents). Information about the event was also published in the web-calendar of Longyearbyen Community Council (Longyearbyen Lokalstyre). A Facebook event was created, and the meeting was advertised on a local Facebook page "Ros and Info". Approximately 25 participants attended the event, Figure 4.

4. List of tangible outcomes:
 - a. List of present problems/issues in the actual coastal stretch.
 - b. List of suggested solutions to the identified problems/issues.
5. Place and time for workshop – studio ARTICA [2], September 5th 2023, 18.00–20.00. Studio ARTICA provides an informal and stimulating space for creative activities. It is well-organized and the "interior" includes printing presses, shelves with books, working tables, a large screen, and chairs. It is not overly big, but small enough such that everyone can be heard during the discussion. The time was chosen to assure that participants could drop by their homes between finishing their daily work and coming to the workshop. Apple cake and coffee were served.
6. Plan for the event:
 - a. To present the CLIMAREST project (the part related to coastal erosion at the Arctic demo site in Longyearbyen).
 - b. To get inputs on problems and solutions at the coastal stretch "City quay – Old quay" in Longyearbyen. This would include short discussion sessions for each category (i.e., for "problems" and "solutions").
7. Meeting agenda:
 - a. Welcome – presentation of the conveyers (Anatoly Sinitsyn and Ingebrigt Uglem)
 - b. Presentation of CLIMAREST, see slides 1 to 5 in [5]
 - c. Introduction to coastal erosion in permafrost coastlines, restoration of marine biodiversity, and ambitions of CLIMAREST, see slides 6 to 12 [5]

- d. Introduction to restoration of nature, see slides 13 to 20 [5]
 - e. Challenges for mitigating coastal erosion in polar regions, see slide 21 in [5]
 - f. Presentation of CLIMAREST Arctic demo site case, see slides 22 to 26 [5]
 - g. Envisioned solution by the key stakeholder, Port of Longyearbyen, see slide 27 in [5]
 - h. CLIMAREST proposal for restoring the coastline in Longyearbyen, see slides 28 to 31 in [5]
 - i. Detailed solutions suggested by CLIMAREST, see slide 32 in [5]:
 - i. Part A: Vision for the whole area "Bykaia-Gammelkaia", see slides 33 to 36 in [5]
 - ii. Part B: Prototype, see slide 37 in [5]
 - iii. Part C: Vision and data collection for replication site at Hiorthamn, see slide 38 in [5]
8. Session to identify the problems/issues – yellow post-it notes and pencils were distributed among the participants, which were asked to write one problem/issue per note. The notes were collected and shoveled, whereupon a number of notes were randomly retrieved. Then the audience were asked if they wanted to reveal who had written the retrieved notes and to elaborate on the notes. Information from notes was recorded in an Excel file [6].
 9. Similar procedure as for the problems/issues was performed for solutions.

CLIMAREST

Kom på workshop om urban kystutvikling!

ClimaRest er et EU-prosjekt hvor vi blant annet forsker på naturhermende løsninger for å beskytte kysten i Arktis mot erosjon. Vi ønsker alle innbyggere i Longyearbyen velkommen til en **åpen workshop** for å samle innspill på behov, synspunkter og ideer for **utvikling av området mellom Bykaia and Gammelkaia**.

Vårt mål er å foreslå og teste en kinderegg-løsning for området som både beskytter mot erosjon, øker biologisk mangfold og øker områdets verdi for lokalbefolkningen. Hvordan bruker du området nå, og hva kunne du tenkt deg å ha der? Er det benker, badstu, badeanlegg eller båtplasser?

Kom til **ARTICA** (Vei 608-3, ved brannstasjonen) **5. september kl. 18** og si din mening! Det blir servert **eplekake og kaffe**.

Kontakt: Anatoly.Sinitsyn@simtef.no /901 76 524, Ingebrist.Uglem@nina.no /934 66 210
Merk at dette er et forskningsprosjekt som løper uavhengig av lokale planprosesser.

Hand-drawn sketches include: "melioring - more holes on the front", "Vokk drift wood", "Local boat", "Lantern", "Sport play ground", "Terrestrial ecosystem", "Human area", "Wind protective wall", "Marine ecosystem", "Human area", "4.11", "Spice forest", "ers", "t", "dag 18/09".

Figure 3. Announcement in SvalbardPosten.

Figure 4. ClimaRest co-creation workshop in action. Pictures: © Anatoly O. Sinitsyn/SINTEF AS and © Zuzanna Swirad.

3. Results

Data from the Excel file [6] was processed in word clouds. For the “issues”, the main group of identified issues can be classified as “human needs”. These include needs such as a pathway for pedestrians, access to water, streetlights, toilets, safety concerns, leisure activities in the area, and aesthetics of constructions (Figure 5). This was followed by requirements for “functionality” and “durability” (both for the coastal protection structure). This included needs such as climate resilience and durability of construction, functionality of tidal ponds (Part B of the CLIMAREST blueprints), control of coastal erosion, and sustainability of construction. Smaller issues related to area conflicts.

Figure 5. Summary of topics for present problems/issues for the coastal stretch "City quay – Old quay" that were identified during the co-creation workshop.

The main group of identified "solutions" related to "recreation", and included aspects such as stairs to access the water, sport and playground facilities, benches, changing rooms, walking path and sauna, toilets, streetlights, street food, limited number of mooring facilities (no big marina; Figure 6). This was followed by solutions related to "sustainability" (art made from marine litter, creation of kelp habitat), and the "planning process" (represented by local involvement, and adaptation to existing plans). Again, for the main issue of "human needs", the main reply was "recreation".

Figure 6. Summary of topics for the suggested solutions for present problems/issues for the coastal stretch "City quay – Old quay" that were identified during the co-creation workshop.

4. Discussion and conclusions

In short, the present problems/issues for the actual coastal stretch were to a large degree related to lacking consideration for human needs. Many of the attendants perceived the area as currently non-functional. Ongoing and visible erosion of the stretch could be why many attendants viewed the area as unstable, and thus highlighted a need for erosion control. The suggested solutions involved to a large degree the construction of sustainable solutions that should accommodate identified human needs by creating opportunities for recreational activities. It was also highlighted that solutions should be planned in an adequate way, and that solutions should be safe and constructed in a way that does not invoke area conflicts.

The workshop was organized as an informal event, and the stakeholders that attended the workshop did not represent an unbiased group of stakeholders since a substantial share of the attendants were students at the local university. Nevertheless, we believe that the outcome of the workshop, at least to a certain extent, may be representative of the overall opinions of the residents in Longyearbyen. The workshop supported our initial belief that the design of structures for erosion control should be a compromise between functionality (erosion control), conservation of biodiversity, sustainability, and human needs (create opportunities for recreational activities in the area). However, the emphasis on human needs/recreational opportunities was stronger than expected, which perhaps could be a result of a skewed composition among the attendants. It was also highlighted that information and involvement during the construction phase would be beneficial.

Author contribution

Sinitsyn, A.O.: conceptualization, input in methodology, writing, editing; Uglem, I.: input in conceptualization, methodology, data curation, writing, editing; Bredin, Y.K.: input in writing, editing.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the participants of the workshop for the discussion and participation in the event; the ARTICA studio for kindly hosting the workshop at their vibrant space; Marta Pujol Martin (SINTEF Ocean AS) for considerations for the co-creation session.

Disclose statement

The authors report no conflict of interests.

Funding

This report was financed by the CLIMAREST project with funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101093865.

Code and Data Availability Statement

Data beyond the manuscript is presented in presentation [5] and in Excel file [6], there is no code to share.

References

1. CLIMARESTproject. *Home page*. Available from: climarest.eu.
2. ARTICA. *Home page*. Available from: <https://www.articasvalbard.no/>.
3. Sinitsyn, A.O., et al., *Development of multiple taliks near settlements on Svalbard – a new source of drinking water for the High Arctic?*, *EGUsphere* [preprint]. 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2023-2950>.
4. American Society® of Civil Engineers. *Home page*. Available from: <https://www.asce.org/>.
5. Sinitsyn, A.O. and I. Uglem, *Towards NBS for coastal protection in cold regions – the ClimaRest perspective*. Workshop "Nature-based Solutions for Coastal Resiliency in the Arctic and Adjacent Regions", 2023. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/11250/3098765>.
6. Uglem, I. and A.O. Sinitsyn, *Results of co-creation workshop held in Longyearbyen (Svalbard) on September 5th 2023*. 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10560746>.
7. Linzbach, A., et al., *Investigations of Coastal Erosion by Means of Laser Scanner VZ-1000 in Vestpynten, Spitsbergen*, in *22nd IAHR International Symposium on Ice*. 2014: Singapore.
8. Guegan, E., *PhD thesis. Erosion of Permafrost Affected Coasts: Rates, Mechanisms and Modelling*, in *Faculty of Engineering Science and Technology, Department of Civil and Transport Engineering*. 2015, Norwegian University of Science and Technology: Trondheim, Norway. p. 203.
9. Jaskólski, M.W., Ł. Pawłowski, and M.C. Strzelecki, *High Arctic coasts at risk—the case study of coastal zone development and degradation associated with climate changes and multidirectional human impacts in Longyearbyen (Adventfjorden, Svalbard)*. *Land Degrad Dev.*, 2018. 29: p. 2514–2524. DOI: 10.1002/ldr.2974.
10. Flyen, A.-C. and M. Boro, *Svalbard: Hiorthhamn Kulturmiljø. Kulturminner og klima – risikovurdering og planlegging av tiltak. En del av prosjekt Adapt Northern Heritage 2020*. 2021, Riksantikvaren.
11. Gann, G.D., et al., *International principles and standards for the practice of ecological restoration. Second edition*. *Restoration Ecology*, 2019. 27(S1): p. S1-S46. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.13035>.
12. NOAA, *Guidance for Considering the Use of Living Shorelines*. 2015. p. 36.
13. SAGE – Systems Approach to Geomorphic Engineering, *Brochure "Natural and Structural Measures for Shoreline Stabilization"*.
14. Interaction Design Foundation – IxDF. *What is Co-Creation?*. *Interaction Design Foundation – IxDF*. 2021, October 27; Available from: <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/co-creation>.